

on the genetic origin of the crosses, with japonica/*O. glaberrima* hybrids responding best, followed by pure japonica varieties and intra-japonica hybrids, japonica/indica hybrids, and pure indica and intra-indica hybrids. The least responsive were pure *O. glaberrima* and intra-*O. glaberrima* hybrids (see figure). Callus production generally peaked 4-5 wk after induction. Calli produced during this period had the greatest probability of yielding green plantlets.

We found a 5:4:1 ratio for haploids, doubled haploids, and polyploids among the regenerated plants regardless of the crosses' genetic origins (see table). The spontaneous doubled haploid lines frequently displayed partial fertility, particularly when derived from *O. sativa/O. glaberrima* crosses and, to a lesser extent, from japonica/indica crosses. High sterility levels might have been due to aneuploidy of the regenerated plants or fixation of sterility genes.

a. Percentage of calli induced and green and albino plantlets produced. J = japonica, I = indica, G = *O. glaberrima*. b. Percentage of calli produced over time.

More than 500 progenies of spontaneous doubled haploid fertile lines of *O. sativa/O. glaberrima* and 600 japonica/indica lines have been evaluated in the field to study their fertility, genetic stability, and agronomic traits. Using the seed from these trials, we are conducting specific screening trials for resistance to the major biotic and abiotic stresses in the region. ■

Ploidy levels of plants regenerated.

Background of pedigrees	Haploid lines (%)	Dihaploid lines (%)	Polyloid lines (%)
Japonica	53	40	7
Japonica and indica	50	45	5
Japonica and <i>O. glaberrima</i>	51	39	10
Mean	51	41	7.3

Response of rice anther culture to short-day treatment

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Japonica rice is widely cultivated in northern China, where the rice-growing season is only 5 mo (May to September) because of the cold climate. It takes 8-10 yr to select a pure line from a cross using conventional rice breeding and at least 4 yr using anther culture. To find ways to further reduce the time needed for rice anther culture, we conducted a study at SRRRI (35.4° N latitude).

Five parental varieties were sown on 18 Feb 1994 and transplanted on 21 Apr. When the seedlings had 7-8 leaves, they were exposed to 9 h of sunshine and 15 h of darkness for 25 d. Before the treatment, 150 ppm multi-effects triazole (MET) was applied to seedlings to

control excessive growth. Crosses were made on 4 Jun, and seeds from five F_1 plants were harvested on 28 Jun. They were sown in pots outside on 2 Jul. The panicles of the five F_1 plants were large enough for sampling on 20 Sep, at which time the micro-spores were in the early- to mid-uninucleate stage.

The same crosses were made in 1993 as checks. They were sown in 1994 on 1 May, and their panicles were sampled on 15 Aug.

Anther calli were induced on N6 medium with 2 mg 2,4-D L^{-1} , 60 g sucrose L^{-1} , 8 g agar L^{-1} , and pH 5.85. The plant regeneration medium was Murashige and Skoog (MS) with 2 mg 6-BAL L^{-1} , 0.5 mg NAAL L^{-1} , 30 g sucrose L^{-1} , 8 g agar L^{-1} , and pH 5.85.

Japonicas in northern China generally head from 15 to 25 Aug and have medium photoperiod sensitivity and medium temperature response. By combining early seeding and short-day treatment in the greenhouse, the five

parents headed from 1 to 5 Jun—nearly 80 d earlier than the same varieties grown in the ricefield under normal cultivation practices (Table 1).

When the panicles of the five F_1 crosses were ready for sampling on 20 Sep, the average day temperature was 19°C, 6°C below that of 15 Aug (the regular sampling date). The anther callus induction and green plantlet regeneration of the five F_1 crosses and their controls were then compared to check the effect of low temperature on anther culture ability. No large differences were found among the five F_1

Table 1. Heading date of five parents. Shandong, China. 1994.

Variety	Short-day treatment	Regular culture
Akenohoshi	4 Jun	23 Aug
89-7013	3 Jun	25 Aug
Xiangqueno	1 Jun	21 Aug
Kinuhikari	31 May	20 Aug
Yakomagokari	1 Jun	16 Aug

crosses and their controls in inducing and differentiating calli (Table 2).

Using early sowing and short-day treatments, the parent plants headed 80 d sooner than those grown under conventional cultivation. It only took 10 mo for the entire anther culture process, from cultivating the parents to growing enough anther lines for transplanting. The improved procedure took 1 yr less than the anther culture technique routinely used in rice breeding. ■

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Table 2. Comparison of anther culture ability of five F₁ crosses. Shandong, China. 1993/94.

Cross	Anthers plated (no.)	Calli produced (%) ^a	Calli plated (no.)	Green plantlets regenerated (%) ^b
<i>Treatment 1^c</i>				
89-7013/Kinuhikari	391	36.57	240	8.33
89-7013/Yamauta	385	30.58	256	51.79
89-7013/Xiangqueno	407	38.56	247	28.67
Akenohoshi/Xiangqueno	416	56.49	243	36.21
Akenohoshi/Yakomagokari	395	42.87	255	34.05
Total	1994	41.01	1241	31.81
<i>Treatment 2^d</i>				
89-7013/Kinuhikari	400	34.50	250	11.60
89-7013/Yamauta	400	33.50	250	50.40
89-7013/Xiangqueno	400	40.25	250	26.40
Akenohoshi/Xiangqueno	400	52.50	250	38.40
Akenohoshi/Yakomagokari	400	46.25	250	32.80
Total	2000	41.40	1250	31.92
^a Anthers producing calli Total anthers plated × 100.		^b Calli producing green plantlets Total calli plated × 100.		^c Crosses made in June 1994.
				^d Check; crosses made in 1993.

Expression of an engineered cysteine proteinase inhibitor (Oryzacystatin-186) in transgenic rice plants

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Meloidogyne spp. (root knot nematodes) damage upland rice in both Asia and Africa. Their wide host range ensures other crops in rotation with rice are at risk in both upland and intermittently flooded, lowland rice.

Hirschmanniella spp. (rice root knot nematodes) also damage lowland rice but only when cropping is intensive. *Pratylenchus* spp. (root lesion nematodes) occur in virtually all Asian and many African upland rice crops and can cause up to 50% yield loss. Our goal is to provide a basis for concomitant control of all nematode pests of rice.

Efficient tissue culture, regeneration, DNA delivery, and selection methodologies have been established for elite African (ITA212, IDSA6, LAC23,

WAB56-104) and Asian (IR64) genotypes.

The plasmids pWRG4517(Δ86 (CaMV 35S-promoter~oc-IΔ86~NOS-polyA) + CaMV35S~ promoter-*aphIV* ~ S-poly A) and pWRG2920 (ubi-5' region ~ *uidA* ~ NOS-polyA) were constructed and used for stable transformation of rice. The *oc-IΔ86* gene was designed by protein engineering to improve the efficacy of native rice *oc-I* against nematodes (Urwin et al 1995). *Oc-IΔ86* differs from *Oc-I* by only one amino acid (Asp86 deleted, Urwin et al 1995). Particle gun bombardment, selection, and regeneration of transformed plants were carried out as previously described (Christou et al 1991). Two days after particle bombardment, the explants were transferred to a medium containing hygromycin to minimize the establishment of chimeric calli (a mix of transformed and non-transformed tissues, Christou and Ford 1995). Twelve days after bombardment, the immature embryos exhibited necrotic areas and large proliferations of embryogenic calli from the scutellum. Embryogenic tissue was repeatedly selected at each subculture. After 3-6 wk, we observed clear differential growth between transformed (hyg+) and nontransformed (hyg-) calli during

proliferation, regeneration, and germination. Transformation of the hyg+ clones was further confirmed by GUS, PCR, Southern blot, and Western blot analyses of regenerated plants. Transformation frequencies were 1-6% from the elite African and Asian genotypes tested (av: ITA212, 2.6%; LAC23, 1.8%; WAB56-104, 1.1%; IDSA6, 1.8%; and IR64, 1.1%). More than 80 independent transformed lines have been obtained to date.

When both pWRG4517Δ86 and pWRG2920 were used for transformation, hyg+ clones and regenerated plants became intensely blue after GUS histochemical staining. In some cases, transformed GUS-negative plants were regenerated from hyg+ clones. When only pWRG4517Δ86 was used, the regenerated plants were first screened by PCR using two primers (AAGAAGACGTTCCAACCACG and GATCTCCAATCTGCGGGATC), amplifying a 1.4-kb fragment containing the *aphIV* gene. Southern blot analysis confirmed the integration of the pWRG4517Δ86 plasmid in the rice genomic DNA (Fig. 1). Levels of oryzacystatin (*Oc-IΔ86*) in plant roots were detected in four of nine transformed rice lines by Western blot analysis (Fig. 2).